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Structural Evolution of MoO₃ Thin Films Deposited on Copper Substrates upon Annealing: An X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy Study

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Abstract: Structural changes of MoO₃ thin films deposited on thick copper substrates upon annealing at different temperatures were investigated via ex situ X-Ray Absorption Spectroscopy (XAS). From the analysis of the X-ray Absorption Near-Edge Structure (XANES) pre-edge and Extended X-ray Absorption Fine Structure (EXAFS), we show the dynamics of the structural order and of the valence state. As-deposited films were mainly disordered, and ordering phenomena did not occur for annealing temperatures up to 300 °C. At ~350 °C, a dominant α -MoO₃ crystalline phase started to emerge, and XAS spectra ruled out the formation of a molybdenum dioxide phase. A further increase of the annealing temperature to ~500 °C resulted in a complex phase transformation with a concurrent reduction of Mo⁶⁺ ions to Mo⁴⁺. These original results suggest the possibility of using MoO₃ as a hard, protective, transparent, and conductive material in different technologies, such as accelerating copper-based devices, to reduce damage at high gradients.

Keywords: molybdenum; TM oxides; XAFS; thin films

1. Introduction

Molybdenum-based oxides are amongst the most adaptable and functional oxides due to their unique characteristics and tunable properties [1–3]. Molybdenum trioxide (MoO₃) is one of the thermodynamically stable molybdenum oxides, with the orthorhombic crystal structure α -MoO₃ [3,4]. The latter phase consists of a set of layers, each one containing distorted MoO₆ octahedra, characterized by three different oxygen sites: a single, a double, and a triple shared site. The dipole nature of the α -MoO₃ layers is at the origin of its relatively high work function (WF) of about 6.5 eV [1,5]. Moreover, despite its insulator nature and high WF, previous studies pointed out that thin MoO₃ films may exhibit a conductive behavior in the presence of defects and oxygen vacancies [6–10] or via interaction with a metallic substrate such as copper [7].

MoO₃ is used in solar cells, batteries, and organic light-emitting diodes (OLEDs), and it is a promising material for protective coatings of accelerating radiofrequency (RF) cavities [5]. In fact, due to the low WF, the performance and the lifetime of a copper RF cavity are strongly affected by breakdown phenomena and thermal stress generated by electron emission from the surface [11]. A high WF conductive coating could be used to reduce these detrimental phenomena, extending the lifetime of the device and allowing it to operate at higher electric fields [1,5,11,12]. Hence, MoO₃ coating can significantly enhance the electronic and mechanical properties of copper-based devices via its high WF and relatively higher hardness, compared with copper [5,13–15], without affecting the surface conductivity. Because the thermal evaporation deposition produces disordered and poorly adhesive MoO₃ coatings [5], with the aim to obtain ordered MoO₃ coatings, we tried to optimize the annealing procedure. This method minimized the formation of MoO₂, which must be avoided, since the slightly off-axis position of Mo atoms in the MoO₂ phase causes the lowering of the WF (~4.6 eV) [3,16]. To establish the optimal annealing temperature for an ordered MoO₃ film on a copper substrate, we investigated the structural evolution of annealed MoO₃ films by X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy (XAF) in X-ray Absorption Near-Edge Structure (XANES) and in the Extended X-ray Absorption Fine Structure (EXAFS) regions [17–20].

2. Materials and Methods

Molybdenum trioxide films were deposited in a dedicated vacuum sublimation set up on 5 mm-thick copper substrates [16]. Molybdenum trioxide powder (99.97% trace metal basis, Sigma-Aldrich®, St. Louis, MO, USA) was heated up to 600 °C in a tungsten crucible inside the evaporation chamber with a base pressure of 10⁻⁵ mbar. In order to anneal the coating without oxidizing the copper substrate, a heat treatment in a low vacuum environment was performed, with a base pressure of 5×10⁻¹ mbar. We also considered a fast heating procedure to minimize the Mo reduction process and to further reduce copper oxidization. This setup allowed us to reach a temperature of up to 500 °C in less than 10 minutes, with a constant heating rate of ~1 °C/sec. After a brief temperature decrease, the samples were exposed to air at 200 °C in order to increase the amount of oxygen in the film [16].

X-Ray Absorption Spectroscopy (XAS) measurements were performed at the B08 beamline at the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF) in Grenoble, which works at the energy of 6 GeV and with a current of ~200 mA in the top-up mode. The B08 beamline is the Italian CRG (LISA), optimized for X-ray absorption measurements. Its optical layout covers a wide range of energies, from 5 to 40 keV, and, with the Si(111) crystals, delivers a flux to the sample of ~10¹¹ ph/s within a spot of ~200 μm [21]. The acquisition at the Mo K-edge (19999 eV) spectra was performed in the energy step-scan mode, and the fluorescence signal was collected by a 12-element Ge detector. The measurements were carried out with an energy resolution in the order of 2 eV, and the scan steps were set to 0.5 eV and 1 eV in the XANES and the EXAFS region, respectively.

X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy (XAS) analysis were performed using the software package FEFF6 (Seattle, WA, USA) [22]. Background subtraction and normalization of the absorption spectra were performed by fitting the pre-edge region with a first-order polynomial, and the spectrum after the edge with a cubic polynomial. The Mo K edge absorption threshold was associated with the first maximum of the first derivative.

3. Results and Discussion

The comparison of XANES spectra at the Mo K edge of the 250 nm MoO₃ films deposited on a copper substrate and annealed at 300 °C, 350 °C, and 500 °C is shown in Figure 1, along with the MoO₃ reference spectrum. The latter has a well-defined pre-edge peak at 20,005.6 eV (peak A), with two other major components at 20,025.7 eV and 20,037.2 eV (peaks B and C). The broadened features of the as-deposited film, in comparison with the reference spectra of the α-MoO₃ spectrum, confirmed that this film was mainly disordered [23–25]. Within the initial annealing stage at 300 °C, the ordering process (flagged by peak C) started to appear, although the film remained disordered. Increasing the annealing temperature to 350 °C triggered an ordering process within the film, leading to the

observation of the typical MoO_3 features (peaks B and C). At the annealing temperature of $500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the spectrum indicated the occurrence of a phase transformation: a clear shift of 3.8 eV of the third component at the energy of $20,033.4\text{ eV}$ (peak C) was observed. This dynamic can be also associated with the partial reduction of Mo ions due to oxygen loss [23,26,27]. A closer look to the XANES spectra also revealed changes in the pre-edge peak as a function of the annealing temperature. Above $350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, we observed a broadening and a lowering of the pre-edge component that can be associated with the partial reduction of Mo^{6+} ions to Mo^{4+} . Indeed, the reduction of the pre-edge intensity, that is a probe of the local and partial empty density of states around Mo atoms, was due to the direct $1s$ to $4d$ quadrupole-allowed transitions and to the dipole-allowed $1s$ hybridized ($5p,4d$) states.

Figure 1. Comparison of X-ray Absorption Near-Edge Structure (XANES) spectra at the molybdenum K edge for the standard $\alpha\text{-MoO}_3$ powder (yellow), the as-deposited MoO_3 film 250 nm thick (grey), and those annealed at $300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (blue), $350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (orange), and $500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (red).

In order to probe the dependence of the structural changes of these oxide films on the annealing temperature, a more detailed XAS analysis was carried out. Figure 2 shows the comparison of the pseudo-radial distribution of the distances in these samples, obtained from the Fourier transform (FT) of the EXAFS $X(k)$ from the as-deposited film, the annealed samples, and the $\alpha\text{-MoO}_3$ reference.

The as-deposited film and the one annealed at $300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ exhibited only a large peak at around 1.7 \AA , corresponding to the nearest oxygen neighbors (Mo–O) without additional shells. This is in agreement with previous XANES spectra of these same samples that pointed out the presence of disordered phases [23]. On the other hand, a structural ordering of the coating was observed at higher annealing temperatures ($> 350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). As shown in Figure 2, at $350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, a split of the first peak appeared, similar to the spectrum of the reference, and a second major component associated with the nearest Mo neighbors (Mo–Mo second shell distance) also emerged at around 3.5 \AA . A comparison with the $\alpha\text{-MoO}_3$ spectrum confirmed the formation of the dominant MoO_3 phase, in agreement with the XANES spectra. At $500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the FT was different from that of the film annealed at $350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, showing a single strong peak due to changes in the first Mo–O shells and in good agreement with the FT of the MoO_2 phase [27]. The Mo–Mo peak at the distance of $\sim 2.5\text{ \AA}$ also appeared, in agreement with the edge-sharing octahedra characteristic of the distorted rutile structure of the MoO_2 phase [27].

Figure 2. Fourier transform (FT) of the $k^3 \cdot \chi(k)$ signal among the disordered MoO_3 film (gray), the $\alpha\text{-MoO}_3$ (yellow), the 300 °C (blue), 350 °C (orange), and 500 °C (red) annealed MoO_3 films deposited on Cu and the $\alpha\text{-MoO}_3$ powder (yellow). The vertical continuous lines refer to the position of MoO_3 main peaks. It is clear that at 500 °C, the distribution is mainly related to MoO_2 , while at 350 °C, it corresponds to the $\alpha\text{-MoO}_3$ phase.

The EXAFS data of the $\alpha\text{-MoO}_3$ reference and annealed films were fitted using the FEFF package with MoO_3 and MoO_2 reference crystalline structures, respectively (see Figure 3). Structural refinements were performed by minimizing the difference of the raw absorption spectra with the simulation, including the structural oscillations, $\chi(k)$, and a suitable background function. The fit was performed in two steps: first, the E_0 and S_0^2 parameters fitting only the first shell were calculated. In the second step, only the distances (R) and σ^2 were left free. During this procedure, we used constant coordination numbers obtained from MoO_3 and MoO_2 crystal structures. The results (see Table 1) of the 350 °C annealed sample returned distances in good agreement with the $\alpha\text{-MoO}_3$ structure, with a reasonable mean-square relative displacement ($\sigma^2 = 0.0015 \text{ \AA}^2$).

Figure 3. (Left) Comparison of the $k^3 \cdot \chi(k)$ and the FT (right) of annealed MoO_3 films deposited on Cu at 350 °C (orange) and 500 °C (red). Corresponding fits are the black dashed lines. The 350 °C signal was fitted with the $\alpha\text{-MoO}_3$ structure, while the 500 °C signal was fitted with the orthorhombic MoO_3 structure.

Table 1. Best-fit values of the samples from Extended X-ray Absorption Fine Structure (EXAFS) spectra. For the 350 °C sample, the fit was obtained from a refinement of the sum of theoretical EXAFS calculated for the orthorhombic MoO_3 structure (k range = 3–12.5 \AA^{-1} ,

$R = 0.5\text{--}4.2 \text{ \AA}$, 8 single scattering paths, 16 free parameters, and two fixed, $r\text{-factor} = 0.027$, $S_0^2 = 0.6$) and a monoclinic MoO_2 structure for the $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ sample (k range = $3\text{--}12.5 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$, $R = 0.5\text{--}4.2 \text{ \AA}$, 6 single scattering paths, 12 free parameters, and two fixed, $r\text{-factor} = 0.021$, $S_0^2 = 0.8$). The coordination numbers are those of the MoO_3 and MoO_2 structures.

$\alpha\text{-MoO}_3$ Reference				350 $^\circ\text{C}$ Annealing				500 $^\circ\text{C}$ Annealing			
Shell	CN	R(\AA)	$\sigma^2(\text{\AA}^2)$	Shell	CN	R(\AA)	$\sigma^2(\text{\AA}^2)$	Shell	CN	R(\AA)	$\sigma^2(\text{\AA}^2)$
Mo-O	1	1.70 ± 0.05	0.0024 ± 0.0004	Mo-O	1	1.70 ± 0.08	0.0015 ± 0.0012	Mo-O	2	1.99 ± 0.07	0.0037 ± 0.0011
Mo-O	1	1.78 ± 0.10	0.0023 ± 0.0003	Mo-O	1	1.80 ± 0.08	0.0013 ± 0.0004	Mo-O	4	2.02 ± 0.05	0.0031 ± 0.0016
Mo-O	2	1.99 ± 0.06	0.0025 ± 0.0002	Mo-O	2	2.07 ± 0.10	0.0021 ± 0.0010	Mo-Mo	2	3.17 ± 0.06	0.0041 ± 0.0012
Mo-O	1	2.22 ± 0.04	0.0022 ± 0.0004	Mo-O	1	2.22 ± 0.11	0.0022 ± 0.0017	Mo-O	4	3.42 ± 0.05	0.0029 ± 0.0010
Mo-O	1	2.31 ± 0.03	0.0022 ± 0.0003	Mo-O	1	2.30 ± 0.05	0.0016 ± 0.0009	Mo-Mo	8	3.73 ± 0.07	0.0037 ± 0.0007
Mo-Mo	2	3.41 ± 0.03	0.0027 ± 0.0003	Mo-Mo	2	3.38 ± 0.05	0.0027 ± 0.0002	Mo-O	4	4.05 ± 0.08	0.0035 ± 0.0005
Mo-Mo	2	3.75 ± 0.02	0.0025 ± 0.0002	Mo-Mo	2	3.73 ± 0.10	0.0019 ± 0.0002				
Mo-Mo	2	4.02 ± 0.09	0.0025 ± 0.0010	Mo-Mo	2	4.08 ± 0.04	0.0019 ± 0.0005				

On the contrary, the fit of the sample annealed at $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ showed a dominant MoO_2 phase, with only the distances of the MoO_2 structure ruling out the contribution of MoO_3 phases. The small deviations of the fit from the experimental spectrum can be associated with the presence of minor amounts of other non-stoichiometric oxide phases.

4. Conclusions

The structural evolution of MoO_3 films deposited on copper after annealing was investigated with XAS spectroscopy. At lower annealing temperatures, the experimental spectra did not change, showing that the as-deposited films were disordered up to $\sim 300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. For the annealing procedure in a low vacuum regime (0.5 mbar) at around $350 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the spectra shows that the film underwent an ordering process, with the formation of the $\alpha\text{-MoO}_3$ phase, as confirmed by the EXAFS analysis. Moreover, XANES spectra at $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ showed that the molybdenum ions underwent a decrease of the pre-edge intensity, in agreement with a reduction from aMo^{6+} to a Mo^{4+} valence state. The fit of the EXAFS spectra showed that the phase of these films could be mainly associated with the presence of the MoO_2 phase. These results represent a first important advancement for many foreseen applications of these coatings, in particular for compact RF devices made of copper.

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Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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